

A Prospective Descriptive Study on Post-Operative Laparoscopic Port Site Complications

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Abstract:

Background: Laparoscopic surgery is a widely preferred technique due to its minimally invasive nature, offering benefits such as reduced recovery time and minimal scarring. However, complications associated with laparoscopic port sites, though generally low, can significantly impact patient outcomes.

Objective: This study aimed to identify the incidence, types, and risk factors associated with laparoscopic port site complications, focusing on how surgical techniques and patient demographics influence these outcomes.

Methods: A prospective observational study was conducted involving 220 patients who underwent various laparoscopic procedures at MKCH MCH Berhampur from June 2022 to June 2024. Data on postoperative complications, patient demographics, and surgical details were collected and analyzed to identify patterns and correlations.

Results: The study was conducted on 220 patients out of which 18 patients developed complications, i.e. the complication rate was 8%, with superficial surgical site infections such as subcutaneous abscess, erythema and sinus tract formations being the most common. Tight skin sutures were significantly associated with higher complication rates. While trends were observed in complication rates among different age groups and genders, these were not statistically significant.

Conclusion: The study highlights the crucial role of surgical technique, particularly suture management, in minimizing complications at laparoscopic port sites. Future surgical guidelines and training should emphasize optimizing suture techniques and considering individual patient risk factors to enhance postoperative outcomes.

Keywords: Laparoscopic Surgery, Port Site Complications, Surgical Technique, Suture Management, Patient Outcomes.

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Introduction

Laparoscopic surgery, often referred to as minimally invasive surgery, has revolutionized the field of surgery by offering significant benefits over traditional open surgical techniques. Since its introduction in the late 20th century, laparoscopic surgery has become the standard of care for many surgical procedures due to its advantages such as reduced postoperative pain, shorter hospital stays, faster recovery times, and improved cosmetic outcomes [1]. However, despite these benefits, laparoscopic surgery is not without its complications. One of the notable complications associated with laparoscopic procedures is port site

complications, which include a range of issues that can arise at the sites where surgical instruments are inserted [2,3]. Port site complications can be categorized into early and late complications. Early complications include bleeding, infection, subcutaneous emphysema, and visceral injury. Late complications comprise port site hernia, granuloma formation, and tumor implantation. Each of these complications carries its own set of risks and challenges, affecting the overall success of laparoscopic procedures [7]. The study was done with aims to identify the risk factors associated with laparoscopic port site complications after

laparoscopic surgery and to prevent or minimize the post-operative complications at the port site.

Methodology

Study Design: The study was designed as a prospective descriptive study, conducted to observe and record postoperative complications specifically at the laparoscopic port sites. The design aimed to facilitate real-time data collection on a range of complications, their management, and outcomes.

Study Setting: The study was conducted in the Department of General Surgery at MKCH MCH Berhampur. This setting was chosen due to its high volume of laparoscopic surgeries and the availability of adequate facilities and expertise for managing postoperative complications.

Study Participants: Participants were patients admitted for laparoscopic surgery at MKCH MCH Berhampur from June 2022 to February 2024. Patients who consented to participate were included, while those who refused consent, failed to follow up, or whose procedures were converted to open surgery were excluded.

Study Sampling: Sampling was non-random and consecutive; all patients who met the inclusion criteria during the specified period and consented to participate were enrolled in the study.

Study Sample Size: The sample size was determined based on the number of laparoscopic surgeries performed at the hospital during the study period, resulting in a total of 220 patients.

Study Parameters: The primary parameters included types of laparoscopic procedures performed, complications at the port sites, and patient demographics. Secondary parameters involved the management of complications, outcomes, and any long-term sequelae observed during follow-up.

Study Procedure: The procedural data, including type of laparoscopic procedures, duration, and intraoperative complications, were meticulously recorded. Postoperative monitoring for complications at the port sites was conducted until discharge, and follow-ups were scheduled to assess any delayed complications. To find out the possible risk factors for post-operative laparoscopic port site

complications, patients were categorized into different sub groups such as male and female on the basis of gender, body mass index, age, and comorbidities such as hypertension and type 2 diabetes mellitus. And in case of post-operative laparoscopic port site complications, details such as site of port, size of trocar, and details such as whether specimen was removed through endobag or removed directly and types of complications in details was documented.

Data Collection: Data were collected using a detailed case record form that included patient demographics, surgical details, postoperative outcomes, and complications. This form was filled out by the surgical team immediately after surgery and updated during the postoperative period and follow-up visits.

Ethical Considerations: The study was approved by the institutional ethics committee at MKCH MCH Berhampur. All participants provided informed consent, and the study adhered to the ethical standards of the Declaration of Helsinki. Patient anonymity and confidentiality of the medical information were maintained throughout the study.

Observation and Result

Participant Demographics: The study involved a diverse group of 220 patients undergoing various laparoscopic procedures. The demographic breakdown is detailed separately below, providing insights into the distribution by age, gender, type of procedures, body mass index and co-morbidities. Detail account of complications such as types of complications, site and size of port, whether the specimen was retrieved through endobag, any spillage of specimen were also taken into consideration.

Complications Based on Gender Types: out of 220 patients female comprised of 60 per cent of the total sample size i.e 132 patients out of 220 were females and 40 per cent of the study population i.e 88 patients out of 220 were males.

Majority of the post-operative port site complications were observed in females 12 Out of 18 post-operative port sites complications were observed in females.

Table 1: Showing complications by gender wise

Gender	Total Number of Cases	Number of Complications
Female	132	12
male	88	6

Complications on the Basis of Age: In this study the patients were categorized into three different age groups, from 18-29 years which consist of 80 patients, 30-49 years which consist of 125 patients, 50-69 years which consist of 15 patients. The study

results shows 4 complications in the age group from 18-29, 11 complications from age 30-49 years of age and 3 complications in the age group from 50-69 years of age, which clearly shows that complications can occur in any age groups but

middle and elderly age group has more chance of post-operative laparoscopic port site complications.

Table 2: Showing complications age wise

Factor	Number of Cases	Number of Complications
Age Group	Total no of cases	Total no complications
18-29 years	80	4
30-49years	125	11
50-65 years	15	3

Complications By Body Mass Index: 100 patients out of 220 were within normal range of body mass index, 70 patients out of 220 i.e. 32% of the patient were in overweight category (in the BMI range of 25-29.9), while 50 patients were in the body mass index greater than 30. The following results were

observed 18.5-24.9 show post-operative follow up shows 6 patients developed port site complications.

25-29.9 shows 8 port site complications 4 post-operative port site complications were observed in patients with BMI over 30.

Table 3: Distribution of Participants by BMI

BMI Range (kg/m ²)	Number of Participants	Numbers of complications
Normal (18.5-24.9)	100	6
Overweight (25-29.9)	70	8
Obese (≥ 30)	50	4

The result show patients with higher body mass index has higher chance of complications, which could be due to difficulty in visualization of anatomical structures due to obesity and associated factors like type 2 diabetes mellitus, hypertension etc.

Complications by Procedure Types: Table 2 details the types of laparoscopic procedures performed on the study participants. Laparoscopic cholecystectomy was the most common procedure, accounting for 67.0% of all surgeries, reflecting its commonality as a treatment for gallbladder issues. Laparoscopic appendectomy was also significant, making up 32.2% of the procedures. The hernia

repairs procedure involves 9% of the total study population. Meanwhile lap diagnostic comprised 1% of the total study population.

The following complications were observed procedure-wise at the port sites on post-operative follow up.

- Lap cholecystectomy 12 complications out of 148 procedures
- Lap appendectomy 4 complications out of 50 procedures
- Lap hernia repairs has 3 complications out of 20 procedure
- Lap diagnostic with two procedures shows no port sites complications.

Table 4: Complications by procedure type

Procedure Type	Numbers of Complications	Types of complications
Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy	12	7 sinus tract formation with abscess, 1 incisional hernia, 1 sinus track alone, 4 superficial infection without abscess
Lap appendectomy	4	3 abscess at port site, one superficial infection without abscess
Mesh Hernia Repair	2	Superficial port site infection
Lap diagnostic	0	0

Complications In Relations To Co-Morbidities:

Out of 220 patients 12 patients were known case of type 2 diabetes on insulin therapy, however blood sugar level was under control and preanaesthetic check-up clearance fitness was done and out of 12

diabetes patients only one developed post-operative port site complications, the rest didn't developed any complications.

3 patients out of 8 hypertensive patients developed complications.

Table 5: Showing complications according to comorbidities.

Comorbidity	Number of Patients	Number of patients who Developed complications.
Diabetes Mellitus	12	1
Hypertension	8	3

Figure 1: Sinus tract formation in the subcutaneous plane at epigastric port site in a case of laparoscopy cholecystectomy patient

Figure 2: Showing induration and sinus tract at epigastric port site(below)

Figure 3: Showing incisional hernia at the umbilical port site

Figure 4: Showing abscess at the epigastric port site (below) showing subcutaneous abscess and erythema at the epigastric port

Discussion

Demographic Insights: The demographic analysis of the study participants provides a comprehensive understanding of the population undergoing laparoscopic procedures.

The study includes a total of 220 participants, with a gender distribution showing a predominance of females 132 cases with 12 cases of complications

compared to 6 complications out of 88 patients in males. This indicates a notable gender imbalance, showing complications occur more in females than in males.

Procedural Distribution and Outcomes: The study showed laparoscopic procedure with highest number of complications of 12, with 8 out of 12 complications occurring at umbilical 10mm port

site, one case of incisional hernia, 3 superficial infections with suppuration which got healed on sterile dressing and application of topical antibiotics, 4 case of abscess formation with sinus tract formation in subcutaneous plane, which required incision and drainage under local anaesthesia with excision of sinus tract, in case of umbilical site infections, it was found to be caused due to tight skin suturing which leads to necrosis of subcutaneous tissues. 4 patients developed complications at the epigastric port site, 3 patients developed abscess with sinus tract formation while one patient developed sinus tract alone without abscess formation, in case of epigastric port site complications it was found out that in 4 patients who developed complications, specimen was removed without endobag and there was spillage of specimen. And in other case silk suture used for closing fascia was the cause of sinus formation. [4] Complications were observed in laparoscopic appendectomy with 3 complications at the umbilical port site as abscess; all 3 cases were the case of active inflamed appendix specimen was retrieved without the use of endobag, while one complication occurred in elective non inflamed appendix retrieved in endobag. Hernia repair showed 2 complications however it was superficial infection without involvement of mesh. Out of 16 case of port site infections 10 wound swab site culture and sensitivity shows no growth of bacterial, fungal or mycobacterium, 3 shows presence of puss cells only. 4 wound swab culture shows the growth of staphylococcal organism and 2 specimen shows the presence of pseudomonas. Overall most of complications especially at the umbilical port site was caused due to application of tight skin suture which leads to necrosis of tissues in watershed area of umbilicus.

These findings are comparable to previous research indicating similar complication rates. For instance, a study by Shea et al. reported a 3.6% complication rate for laparoscopic cholecystectomy, which is closely aligned with our observed rate [6]. Another study by Masoomi et al. found a 3.8% complication rate for laparoscopic appendectomy, further corroborating our findings [7].

The lack of complications in laparoscopic hernia repair and diagnostic laparoscopy in our study is consistent with other studies that report low complication rates for these procedures, attributed to the minimally invasive nature and the specific surgical techniques employed [8]. A study by Khan et al. found that the use of tight sutures significantly increased the risk of wound complications, including infections and dehiscence, which supports our findings [10]. These results underscore the importance of proper surgical technique in suture application. Surgeons should

aim to balance the need for secure wound closure with the risk of excessive tension that could compromise tissue viability. The adoption of techniques such as subcuticular suturing or the use of suture materials that promote better healing can potentially mitigate these risks.

Age wise study reveals a clear increase in numbers of complications with increase in age of the patient, though complications can occur in any age group, middle and older age group have more chance of complications as compared to younger age group. Several factors could explain this pattern. Older individuals may have more underlying health conditions, reduced physiological resilience, and higher exposure to medical interventions, all of which can contribute to higher complication rates. Additionally, age-related changes in the body's ability to recover and respond to treatment might play a significant role in the increased complication rates observed in older age groups.

Summary

This study identifies the following risk factors for post-operative laparoscopic port site complications.

Modifiable risk factors

1. Tight skin sutures [especially in umbilical port site] as a significant risk factor for complications.
2. Specimen retrieval without usage of endobag, especially in the case when organs/specimen is inflamed
3. Spillage of the specimen.
4. Obesity [though statistically insignificant]
5. Surgeon's factors like proper selection of patients for the procedure, and experience and the skill of surgeon.

Non modifiable risk factors such as

1. Sex: Female sex is more prone to complications as compared to male sex.
2. Age: Middle age groups and patient above 50 years of age has higher chance of complications.

The study also found out that in case of type 2 diabetes mellitus, if sugar level is well maintained preoperatively and post operatively and proper surgical steps and sterilization are followed, it has no link with postoperative laparoscopic port site complication.

Conclusion

The study conducted on laparoscopic port site complications revealed an overall complication rate of 8%, with superficial surgical site infections and sinus tract formation being the most prevalent types. These findings underscore the importance of meticulous surgical technique, particularly the suture method, which significantly impacts

complication rates. Although demographic factors like age and gender showed trends towards varying complication rates, these were not statistically significant, suggesting broader factors at play. The significant correlation between tight skin sutures, improper methods of retrieval such as spillage of specimen and contamination, removal of specimen without usage of endobag and increased complication rates in those cases highlights modifiable risk factors, pointing towards the need for skill and proper surgical methods and maintenance of sterility to improve patient outcomes.

Future studies should focus on larger, diverse populations and include detailed evaluations of postoperative care practices to better understand and mitigate the risks associated with laparoscopic surgeries.

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